

The influence of water saving and foliar organic fertilizer on shallot production in dryland of NTB

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ABSTRACT

The reduction of the risk of agricultural failure due to climate change was implemented in the NTB province through conservation agriculture (CA) with three main pillars: minimum tillage or no tillage, continuously land cover crop and plant rotation or intercropping. Conservation agriculture in the long term may improve yields and simultaneously increase adaptation to climate change, especially in erratic rainfall conditions. The objective of this research was to apply conservation agriculture technology on dryland and semiarid climate type for maize cultivation through participatory approach. There were 46 farmer groups with a total of 953 members have involved to apply conservation agriculture through a field school approach. Each farmer group developed a CA plot as a joint learning tool compared to farmer practices. Farmer groups planted maize at all types of CA. This activity was conducted at 3 districts, 5 sub-districts and 9 villages in NTB province from 2014 to 2016. The average yield of maize crops with conservation agriculture during the four planting seasons from 2014 to 2016 was 3.9 ton/ha with an increase of 77% compared to the harvest of maize by the farmer practices (2.2 ton/ha). The average yield of maize in the rainy season of 2014 with CA techniques was 4.3 ton/ha; this yield was increase by 68% compared to farmer practice (2.6 ton/ha). In wet season of 2015, the average yield of maize with CA was 3.4 tons / ha and this was increased by 87% compared to farmers practices (1.8 tons / ha). Similar trend was also found in wet season of 2016 where yield of maize increased by 63% compared to farmers practices. Thus, Conservation agriculture consistently increased maize productivity and increased the income of farmers on uncertain climatic conditions.

Keywords: shallot, dryland, bio-urine, water saving, sprinkler irrigation, farrow irrigation.

INTRODUCTION

West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) with a land area covered for about 2.01 million hectares, has 84 percent or about 1.8 million hectares of dryland (BPS,

2016). NTB has the largest dryland area in Indonesia after NTT. The dryland of NTB has not been used optimally to increase food production and so far the Government prioritized to develop wet land which may spur the inequality of farmer welfare in dryland.

Most of the land in West Nusa Tenggara Province, generally, is less fertile which has various limiting factors (physical, chemical and biological soil) that lead to low productivity (Ministry of Agriculture, 2009). Dryland required site-specific management and technology to increase production. Revitalization of policy and acceleration of dryland development may be a strategic option to improve the welfare of rural communities as most of the poor people in NTB live in the dryland and most of their livelihoods are dependent on agricultural activities on dryland. The existence of the agricultural development program in dryland would reach the poor community directly to improve their welfare.

Agriculture as a major source of livelihood in West Nusa Tenggara is very vulnerable to climate change. Climate change is the most stressful factor in decreasing productivity and production in the agricultural sector. Most dryland area has been planted once every year on wet season due to low and erratic rainfall. Food shortages especially in unfavorable seasons due to extreme climate change becomes challenges in NTB and its impact on smallholder households that have relatively limited land resources (subsistence). Furthermore, the influence of climate change has exacerbated by lack of sustainability land and crop management such as high erosion occurred, intensive tillage, land clearing by burning and excessive use of chemicals pesticide and fertilizers. This degradation of the land resource base has reduced crop yields and productivity factor, which forced farmers, scientists and development stakeholders to look for an alternative paradigm that is ecologically sustainable as well as profitable. Another challenge for agriculture is its environmental foot print and climate change. Agriculture is responsible for about 30% of the total greenhouse gas emissions of CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ while being directly affected by the consequences of a changing climate (IPCC, 2007).

Sustainable crop production intensification must not only reduce the impact of climate change on crop production but also mitigate the factors that cause climate change by reducing emissions and by contributing to carbon sequestration in soils. Intensification should also enhance biodiversity in crop production systems above and below the ground to improve ecosystem services for better productivity and healthier environment. A set of soil-crop-nutrient-water-landscape system management practices known as Conservation Agriculture (CA) has the potential to deliver on all of these goals (Hobbs, et al., 2012; Kassam et al., 2009; Friedrich et al., 2012).

According to FAO (2011), Conservation Agriculture (CA) is a farming

system that promotes maintenance of a permanent soil cover, minimum soil disturbance (i.e. no tillage), and diversification of plant species. It enhances biodiversity and natural biological processes above and below the ground surface, which contribute to increased water and nutrient use efficiency and to improved and sustained crop production. CA is characterized by three linked principles, namely: 1. Continuous no- or minimal mechanical soil disturbance (i.e., no-tillage and direct sowing or broadcasting of crop seeds, and direct placing of planting material in the soil; minimum soil disturbance from cultivation, harvest operation or farm traffic, in special cases limited strip tillage); 2. Permanent organic soil cover, especially by crop residues, crops and cover crops; and 3. Diversification of crop species grown in sequence or associations through rotations or, in case of perennial crops, associations of plants, including a balanced mix of legume and non legume crops (FAO, 2011; Friedrich et al., 2012).

Conservation Agriculture seeks to reduce risks due to extreme climate change through reducing soil tillage or zero tillage, permanent land cover, and crop rotation that may lead to increase population of soil organisms and organic carbon (Corsi et al., 2012), reducing the use of chemicals pesticides and fertilizers (Hobbs et al., 2012). Labor requirements are generally reduced by about 50%, which allows farmers to save time, fuel and machinery costs (Saturnino and Landers, 2002; Baker et al, 2007; Lindwall and Sonntag, 2011; Crabtree, 2010). Fuel savings in the order of around 65% are in general reported (Sorrenson and Montoya, 1984; 1991). Through this approach it is expected that agricultural yields would increase the quality of land and water resources (Laurent et al., 2011). The introduction of the principles and practices of conservation agriculture to farmers and other stakeholders was carried out through some stages, including training at provincial, district, sub-district and farmers levels, practices and trials by farmers and field extensions. The implementation of Conservation Agriculture in West Nusa Tenggara means to increase maize production, improve soil structure and fertility. The objective of this research was to apply conservation agricultural technology on dryland and semiarid climate type for maize cultivation through participatory approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The assessment was conducted at farmer field in Labuhan Lombok Village, Pringgabaya District, East Lombok Regency, which is a stretch of dryland semiarid agro-ecosystem area and one of the shallot production centers in NTB on June 2017. The study was designed for Split plot design with 2 main plots (sprinkler and farmer practice (farrow) irrigation method) and sub-plot was concentration of bio-urine (0, 5%, 10%, 15% and 20%) with three replication

at plot size of 100m². Enriched organic manures with *Trichoderma* SP at 10 ton/ha were also applied at the time of plowing soil. Shallot cultivation system referred to the technical guidance on shallot integrated plant management (PTT) (Sumarni and Hidayat, 2005). Bio-urine treatments were applied using sprayer starting at 20 days after planting each week for 4 times. Sprinklers irrigation treatment were set up for each plot and irrigated plant every two days depending on soil moisture and plant growth. Farrow irrigation treatment were applied according to farmer practice. Water meter was installed for both sprinkler and farrow irrigation treatments in order to record water used for each irrigation treatment.

Some parameters were measured during the experiment such as:

- a. plant height and leave amount; measured at harvest. These parameters were taken at 6 hills per plot
- b. Fresh weight at harvest; was taken at harvest stage by sampling at 1m² for 3 times each plot
- c. Dry weight; all fresh sampling were sun dried for 10 days and weighed amount
- d. Amount of clove (tuber)/hill was measured at 6 hills/plot
- e. Diameter of clove/hill

Data were analysed using analysis of variance (annova) using the Genstat Software (Version 9.2.0.153, VSN International Ltd, Oxford). When one or more treatments had a significant effect on a measured parameters, least significant difference (LSD) was calculated to compare mean values of treatments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil and agroclimate characteristics of the site

Soil characteristics in the assessment site has shown in Table 1. In general, the soil conditions in the study location are quite fertile in terms of chemistry, where the nutrient content of phosphor and potassium were at a high status, while the nitrogen status was low. The pH of the soil was in a range of neutral to slightly alkaline. The ability of the soil to hold water in the study area was quite low due to low clay content and soil organic matter. The percentage of clay at the site was about 10% at 0-10 cm layer and decreases to 6% at a soil depth of 20-40cm. The soil texture at the study site was regarded as sandy loam. Thus application of farrow irrigation may less suitable in the location. However, farmer has practiced farrow irrigation for long time.

The climate condition of the site has regarded as dryland and semi-arid agro-ecological zone with annual rainfall was less than 1000 mm/year and was grouped as climate type of D and E (Oldemen et al, 1980) (Figure 1). Topography of the site was relatively flat with dominated by Entisols soil type.

Although annual rain fall was limited for crop to grow, there has a source of irrigation water available that can be used for irrigation in this area called deep water pumped. This pumped water usually used for irrigating crop at dry season during April to November while during wet season of December to March, water irrigation for crop was from rain fall.

Table 1. Soil physical and chemical properties of the experiment site

Soil	pH-H ₂ O	pH-KCl	EC	N Total	Organic-C	P ₂ O ₅ Olsen	CEC	K	Na	Ca	Mg
Layer	pH-meter		μS/cm	%	%	ppm	cmol/kg	cmol/kg			
0-10	7.95	6.52	0.140	0.250	0.807	58.87	18.83	2.73	3.70	13.63	3.60
10-20	7.91	6.51	0.103	0.167	0.602	52.30	16.37	0.77	1.77	8.73	3.13
20-40	7.97	6.71	0.170	0.120	0.273	41.80	19.40	1.33	2.03	12.43	3.57
Soil layer	Texstur (%)			Bulk Density	Wilting point	Field capacity	Water available	Infiltration rate			
	sand	silt	clay	gr/cm ³	point	% volume		cm/h			
0-10	57	33	10	1.08	11.29	29.19	17.90	5.38			
10-20	56	36	9	1.1	13.23	28.83	15.60	6.02			
20-40	54	40	6	1.08	10.98	24.93	11.95	4.98			

In Pringabaya Subdistrict, there are 72 units of groundwater irrigation development wells (P2AT) with varying discharge around 10-20 L / sec. P2AT well can irrigate varied of land size in range of 15-20 ha. Cost for irrigating plant vary starting from Rp. 30,000 to Rp 35,000 per hour and one ha of land may take about 20-23 hours.

Figure 1. Monthly average rainfall variation for 17 years (2000-2016) at experiment site.

Bio-urine properties used

Biourine used was produced by Tunas Maju farmers livestock group, Setanggor Village, Praya Barat sub-district of Centre Lombok District. Biourine is a liquid organic fertilizer made from cattle urine through a fermentation process. The biourin characteristics used in this study has shown in Table 2.

Animal manure is separated between solid waste to be used as raw material for compost and liquid waste as a material for making bio-urine. The urine is then fermented for 10 days. The fermenters used were *Rumino bacillus* and *Azotobacter*, each with a dose of 1.25 ml/liter urine. The fermented urine is then aerated to remove excess ammonia for 4 days and ready to be applied for crop (Nazam et al 2017).

Table 2. Bio-urine characteristic used in this experiment

No	Parameters	Composition
1	C-Organic	4%
2	N-total	1,05%
3	C/N ratio	7,40
4	K ₂ O	1,31%
5	Fe total	148,24 ppm
6	Mn	10,89 ppm
7	Zn	3,26 ppm
8	Cu	0,73 ppm
9	Bacillus sp	3,10x10 ⁴ CPU
10	Azotobacter	9,0x10 ³ CPU

Agronomic and yield parameters of shallot.

Shallot plant were harvested at 63 days after planting. The influence of water saving and bio-urine as foliar organic fertilizer on agronomic parameters of shallot has shown in Table 3. In general, both treatments of water irrigation and concentration of bio-urine have varied effects on agronomic parameters of shallot. The irrigation types (sprinkler and farrow) and concentration of bio-urine significantly effected fresh yield of shallot, although there was not significant effect on the interaction of these treatments. Fresh yield of shallot was higher at farrow irrigation type (29.47 ton/ha) than that of sprinkler irrigation (26.14 ton/ha). This also indicated by there was significant effect of irrigation types on water contents and plant height of shallot. However, when the shallot yield were dried under sun for 10 days, dry yield was not significantly different between sprinkler and farrow irrigation types. In general practice, farmers usually dry shallot under the sun before selling to market due to good price gained. Others parameters such as amount of hill/m², amount of leave/hill, tuber/hill and diameter tuber/hill were not significantly affected by types of irrigation, indicating that the quality of shallot produced by sprinkler irrigation may not be significantly different with farrow irrigation.

The influence of biourine on fresh and dry yield of shallot is shown in Figure 1. Fresh yield was affected by concentration of bio-urine in both farrow

and sprinkler irrigation typed although there was no significant interaction effect. The lowest yield of shallot was found at control (no biourine applied) ie 20.2 ton/ha and the highest yield was found at 15% biourine application. Yield increased as concentration of biourine increased, then it was decrease at 20 % although this was not significantly different with 15% or 10% of biourine application. This trend of fresh yield was similar to the trend of dry yield of shallot. Other parameters such as amount of hill/m², amount of leave/hill, tuber/hill and diameter tuber/hill were not significantly affected by concentration of biourine. This indicated that the quality of shallot has affected by application of biourine. Thus, It may be summarized that optimum concentration of biourine to be applied to shallot cultivation is 12%.

Table 3. Agronomic parameters of shallot as influence by irrigation and biourine concentration treatments in dryland and semi-arid of NTB

Irrigation types	Bio-urine (%)	Hill/m ²	Fresh yield t/ha	dry yield (t/ha)	% water	Height (cm)	Leave amount/hill	Tuber/hill	tuber diameter (cm)
Sprinkler	0	35.3	19.7	13.1	33.2	36.3	26.0	7.7	1.7
	5	36.7	22.3	15.2	32.2	38.7	28.3	7.7	1.7
	10	40.0	29.0	18.8	35.2	48.7	37.0	5.7	2.3
	15	43.0	32.3	20.4	37.0	46.7	47.0	7.0	2.2
	20	37.3	27.3	15.7	42.6	41.0	27.0	6.0	2.3
Farrow	0	36.0	20.7	13.3	35.5	37.0	28.3	7.7	1.8
	5	36.3	22.7	15.3	32.3	52.3	39.7	8.0	2.2
	10	39.0	35.0	22.8	35.0	52.0	42.3	8.0	2.1
	15	43.0	35.7	21.9	38.7	54.3	40.0	7.3	2.1
	20	41.0	33.3	19.7	40.8	54.7	49.0	8.0	2.0
	main plot (S)	ns	*	ns	*	*	ns	Ns	ns
F-test	Sub-plot (U)	ns	***	***	ns	***	*	Ns	ns
	S x B	ns	ns	ns	ns	**	*	Ns	ns

Figure 1. Influence of biourine on fresh and dry yield of shallot in dryland of NTB

Water used during growth period of shallot

The amount of water applied during shallot growth period was monitored using water meter tool which is shown in Table 4. The amount of water needed by using sprinkler during plant growth (63 days) was 343.8 mm. The amount of water is much lower when compared to farrow irrigation practiced by farmers. It has recorded that there was 10 times irrigation applied by farmer during shallot growth duration. Each time of irrigation needed about 22.5 hours/ha at flow rate of 7.9 liter/sec. Based on our calculation, that the amount of water irrigation used during shallot growth period using farrow irrigation was 631.8 mm (Table4). This shows that was 84% of irrigation water can be saved by sprinkler type compared to farmer practiced.

Tabel 4. Water used during shallot growth period between sprinkler and farmers practice irrigation types in dryland of NTB.

Growth stages	Duration (days)	Sprinkler (mm)	Farrow (farmer practice)
Soil wetting		64	64
Early growth	15	88.4	135
Optimum growth	25	93.5	225
Maximum growth	15	77.7	135
Mature	8	20.2	72
Total	63	343.8	631.8

CONCLUSIONS

Productivity of shallots has influenced by the concentration of biourine and irrigation types. Fresh yield of shallot was higher in farrow irrigation than that of in sprinkler irrigation but this was not significantly different on dry yield of shallot. Biourine was able to increase shallot yield from 20.2 tons/ha to 34.0

tons/ha of fresh weight at a concentration of 15%. This has increased by 63%. It has suggested that the optimum biourine application to increase the shallot yield is 12% in the range at 20-45 days after planting. The amount of water used by sprinkler irrigation during plant growth (63 days) was 343.8 mm which was lower than that practiced by farmers (631.8 mm). This shows that was 84% of irrigation water can be saved by sprinkler type compared to farmer practiced.

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